

LoKit: A Toolkit for Building Distributed Collaborative Applications

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Abstract

LoKit is a new toolkit built on top of the coordination language LO. It allows for building distributed collaborative applications providing a set of generic tools.

This paper shortly introduces the concept of the toolkit, presents a subset of LoKit-tools, and finally, demonstrates its power by discussing an example application created by the toolkit.

Keywords: fault-tolerant communication, coordination, toolkit, LO.

1 Introduction

This paper presents the basic design decisions and first results for a new toolkit residing on top of the coordination language LO.

The underlying language

LO is a rule-based coordination language designed for managing multiple software agents in open systems. LO can be applied for implementing systems whose behavior is generated by the interaction of autonomous, heterogeneous components. In general, with LO you can flexibly customize and efficiently execute complex multi-agent coordination schemata. It is important to understand in which sense LO – and therefore the tools provided – is a *coordination* language, versus a programming language in the traditional sense. This essentially means that LO is just concerned about the coordination and communication of events among agents, while traditional “procedural” activities (data-structure manipulation, arithmetics etc.) are delegated to the programs embedded in the agents themselves. Nowadays a language like LO is, therefore, called *middleware*.

The basic features of the language are the @-construct for tight coordination, the &-construct for loose coordination, and the ^-construct for broadcast communication. The main uses of these constructs are as follows. Firstly, to inform the agents about actions being performed within the distributed environment (monitoring, etc.), secondly, to coordinate the actions performed by a *single* agent and, finally, to support actions involving *multiple* agents, such as allocating/replicating resources among different nodes in the network [8, 9], or archiving/retrieving geographically dispersed information.

The @-construct for tight coordination is called *par* because it assumes that all resources on the left-hand side of a rule are consumed in parallel under the all-or-nothing principle and that all

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resources on the right-hand side are produced. The $\&$ -construct for loose coordination is called *with* because it assumes that all resources at the left hand side of a rule are consumed in parallel under the all-or-nothing principle and that all resources on the right hand side of a rule separated by ' $\&$ ' are produced as replicas that act in parallel. The \wedge -construct for broadcast communication is realized over any transport layer that provides communication between – if necessary – heterogeneous sites.

It is beyond of scope of this paper to explain the full functionality and semantics of the LO-language; for more details see [3, 4, 5, 6].

The toolkit

The aim of most CSCW-toolkits for building distributed applications is to reduce development effort, to enable rapid prototyping, and to increase the product quality of collaborative applications, e.g., GroupKit [19] for real-time conferencing, Strudel [22] for email-based workflow management, or DistEdit [15] for distributed editing.

The aim of LoKit is to provide coordination between applications rather than providing applications themselves. The design of LoKit is based on the following two main toolsets. Firstly, the basic coordination toolset is of interest where coordination is achieved both between multiple applications on a single host and between multiple applications that run on different hosts. The operating systems used at the different hosts (multi-vendor PCs and workstations) may range from PC-based Windows to NT, UNIXes or OS/2. All communication is done within a client-server model, i.e., there are clients (typically PCs) requesting tasks that involve coordination and servers that provide the tasks in question.

Secondly, the higher level toolset is an important issue. LoKit provides tools for system support such as different styles of communication, failure handling, and transactions. As far as the different communication styles are concerned, the tools provide modules for RPC-like communication, one-way message-passing, both blocking (like CSP [14]) and non-blocking (like Actor-systems [1]). Furthermore, it handles queries with multiple replies and finally, fully-symmetric communication. In this way, instead of providing simple transport-level messaging (like send-message and receive-message primitives), the toolkit provides high-level mechanisms that are more appropriate for CSCW-applications. The full set of higher level tools is generic and provides an easy way to implement different applications.

Organization of the paper

Sect. 2 starts with a discussion of two styles of communication the toolkit provides, namely RPC-style and query-style. The discussion includes a description of the generic rules for both non-replicated and replicated servers, where the number of replicas may a priori be unknown (e.g., during a WAIS lookup). Moreover, rule sets are introduced that can handle timeouts within the declarative LO-environment of the toolkit. In Sect. 3 an example for remote banking is briefly discussed that serves as a real-life application to demonstrate both the appropriateness of the model and the usability of LO and the toolkit itself. Finally, Sect. 4 addresses topics for further research.

2 LoKit-primitives for communication

Most of the applications within the area of interest need some form of communication among distributed processes. We provide amongst others, the basic mechanisms for RPCs and queries. Fig. 1 illustrates RPC-style and query-style forms of communication with a single client and replicated servers. Multiple replicas of the servers are installed to implement a reliable service (see [23] for a replicated RPC library for the Amoeba distributed operating system).

For each of the these communication styles we discuss a possible LO-realisation in terms of

Figure 1: Two example styles of communication.

generic rules and coordination features provided by the language. We motivate the decisions and give some remarks for further extensions such as availability policy.

Within the description of the generic rules sometimes there is a need for system-calls, system-dependent calculations, or application-dependent executions. *Resources* of this kind and real triggers are printed in small capital letters, e.g., `GET_UNIQUE(RPCId)` or `LOOKUP`. Keywords of the generic rules are printed in bold face (e.g., **client**), parameters and variables are printed in italic (e.g., *C*).

2.1 RPC-style connection

An RPC-style connection is a synchronous communication, where a client and a server together fulfill a certain task.¹ The communication is initiated by the client. It is a single outbound flow (typically a request) with a single response/reply (see a single client-server-relation in Fig. 1 – RPC-style).

In the following, we show the LO-level coordination part of the RPC-communication, both with and without replication of servers.

RPC without replication of servers

Under the assumption that there is only one provider (i.e., a single server) for a particular service, the rules for connecting a client with a server are quite simple. In fact, the client simply sends out a request to all possible locations where the server could reside. It then waits for the reply to arrive as a message from a server. To make things simple, for the time being, we do not discuss time, i.e., here we simply assume that the reply to the request will eventually arrive. Later, of course, the client will use some timeout mechanism to cover the case where a reply is never received.

(R1) *client: initiate RPC-request*

client(*C*)

⊙ `GET_UNIQUE(RPCId)`

⊙ *some_trigger*

⊙ `^msg_request(RPCId,param0,...,paramN)`

→ **client**(*C*,**blocked**,*RPCId*).

¹We are well-aware of the existence of deferred synchronous communication and asynchronous RPCs where placeholders for the return information (e.g., the *futures* in *Cronus* [12, 13] or Liskov’s and Shriram’s *promises* [17]) are used and where the client may proceed until the return values are really needed. Ananda *et al.* give a comprehensive survey of asynchronous RPCs in [2].

(R2) *server: produce result and reply to RPC-request*

```
server(S)  
@ msg_request(RPC_Id,param_0,...,param_N)  
@ PRODUCE(RPC_Id,param_0,...,param_N,result)  
@ ^msg_reply(server(S),RPC_Id,result)  
→ server(S).
```

(R3) *client: consume RPC-reply*

```
client(C,blocked,RPC_Id)  
@ msg_reply(server_Id,RPC_Id,result)  
@ CONSUME(server_Id,RPC_Id,result)  
→ client(C).
```

(R1) The client initiates the RPC-style connection when the trigger is consumable, e.g., a trigger-event from the user interface or a particular trigger message from outside. The client sends the request to the possible locations of the server that should handle the request. The RPC-request itself has a unique identifier (*RPC_Id*) in order to connect the request-reply activity, i.e., it serves for the communication binding. The unique identifier is created through the system-level command `GET_UNIQUE(RPC_Id)`. Furthermore, the request carries $N+1$ parameters to fulfill the request at the server side. In a RPC-style connection, parameter *param₀* is typically the name of the procedure to be invoked.

(R2) The corresponding server is triggered by the request message. It carries out the request by producing a result that is sent back in a reply message to the initiator of the request. The initiator of the request is already in blocked mode (**client**(*C,blocked,RPC_Id*)). In the current implementation the production of the result is done in a low-level Prolog implementation that depends on the task to fulfill.

(R3) The blocked client that is triggered by the reply message with the corresponding *RPC_Id* consumes the result offered by the server *server_Id*.

RPC with replication of servers

Under the assumption that there are possibly more providers (i.e., multiple identical servers) for a particular service, the rules for connecting a client with these servers become more complicated. The client sends out a request to all possible locations where the servers could reside. It then waits for the replies to arrive as different messages from these servers.

In many applications, the number of servers are a priori unknown. After starting, for instance a world-wide WAIS search, the number of servers contacted and willing to reply cannot be predicted. Since it is not realistic and sometimes impossible to wait for the replies of all servers, we provide different instances of the client w.r.t. answers received. First of all there is the “main” client that waits for the first reply to arrive. As soon as the first reply has been consumed, this client may proceed (as in the implementation shown below).

In parallel, this client creates another instance of itself, the so-called *catch-follow-up* client. This catch-follow-up client, and all further catch-follow-up clients that are created in the same way, will process the other replies from the “slower” servers.

(Rr3) *client: consume RPC-reply and spawn catch-follow-up client*

```
client(C,blocked,RPC_Id)  
@ msg_reply(server_Id,RPC_Id,result)  
@ CONSUME(server_Id,RPC_Id,result)  
→ client(C)  
& client(C,catch_follow-up,RPC_Id).
```

(Rr4) *catch-follow-up client: consume other RPC-reply and spawn new catch-follow-up client*

client(*C*,**catch_follow-up**,*RPC_Id*)

⊙ **msg_reply**(*server_Id*,*RPC_Id*,*result*)

⊙ CONSUME(*server_Id*,*RPC_Id*,*result*)

→ **client**(*C*,**catch_follow-up**,*RPC_Id*).

(Rr1) As in the case with no replication of servers, the client initiates the RPC-style connection when the trigger is consumable and blocks. The client broadcasts the request to all possible servers that are able to handle the request. Note, however, that all of them get a copy of the request.

(Rr2) For each of the servers, as before in the non-replicated case.

(Rr3) The blocked client that is triggered by the reply message with the corresponding *RPC_Id* consumes the first result offered by one of the servers. Furthermore, another client process is spawned that consumes (e.g., by deleting them) the follow-up server-replies of the *RPC_Id*-request that is already handled.

(Rr4) For every single RPC there exists such a client process that consumes the follow-up server-replies of the *RPC_Id*-request that is already handled. We have not provided a termination policy for these processes yet. In fact, we do not know how many replies will be received for a single request because we do not want to count active servers (this is part of a possible availability policy). Furthermore, we do not know how long it takes until the last reply is received. Again at this level, we do not want to install a time-out scheme. This should be part of the availability policy as well. During the lifetime of our system a lot of processes will be created (as a matter of fact, resources) of the form **client**(*C*,**catch_follow-up**,*RPC_Id*). To get rid of them, a garbage collector in every pool can be defined that deletes such “processes” that are waiting for RPC-replies of obsolete requests.

Another, more elegant, possibility is implemented using our timeout policy. Here the catch-follow-up clients are terminated (LO-notation: **#t**) without any intervention from administrators simply using a side-effect. More about this in Sect. 2.3.

2.2 Query-style connection

A query-style connection is a synchronous connection between a client and some server. The client sends out a single outbound flow of data (the query-request) and receives multiple replies in a chain (see a single client-server-relation in Fig. 1 – query-style).

Query without replication of servers

Assuming that there is only one server for a particular service, the client simply sends out a request to all possible locations where the server could reside. It then waits for the reply to arrive as *multiple* messages from this server.

(Q1) *client: initiate query-request*

client(*C*)

⊙ GET_UNIQUE(*query_Id*)

⊙ *some_trigger*

⊙ ^**msg_query**(*query_Id*,*param*₀,...,*param*_{*N*})

→ **client**(*C*,**blocked**(1),*query_Id*).

(Q2) *server: produce replyno-th result and reply to query-request*

– set of rules, not shown –

(Q3) *client: consume replyno-th reply*

client(*C*,**blocked**(*replyno*),*query_Id*)

⊙ **msg_reply**(*server_Id*,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)

⊙ CONSUME(*server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked**(*replyno* + 1),*query_Id*).

(Q4) *client*: consume *replyno*-th and last reply
client(*C*,**blocked**(*replyno*),*query_Id*)

⊙ **msg_reply**(*server_Id*,**replyno_last**,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 ⊙ CONSUME(*server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*).

(Q1) The client initiates the query-style connection when the trigger is consumable and blocks for the first reply to be received. As in RPC-style connection there is a strict communication binding. The query itself has a unique identifier (*query_Id*) to connect the different request-reply activities to one task. The unique identifier is created by the system-level command GET_UNIQUE(*query_Id*). Again, the request carries $N+1$ parameters to fulfill the request at the server side where parameter *param₀* is the name of the query procedure to be invoked.

(Q2) Analogously to the server site rule in the RPC-cases, a corresponding server is triggered by the query message. It carries out the request by producing multiple results that are sent back in a several reply messages to the initiator of the query. Since LO is an asynchronous coordination language, we cannot guarantee that all replies of a server are received in order (even when the network protocol used provides this feature). Every reply message, therefore, is tagged with a unique *replyno* ranging from 1 to *n*, e.g., **msg_reply**(**server**(*S*),1,*query_Id*,*result*) for the first reply message. The last message is additionally tagged with **replyno_last**, i.e., the last message out of *n* messages that are sent back to the client has the following form: **msg_reply**(**server**(*S*),**replyno_last**,*n*,*query_Id*,*result*).

(Q3) The blocked client that is triggered by the *replyno*-th reply message with the corresponding *query_Id* consumes the *replyno*-th result offered by the server. Then the client blocks for the next reply to be received by the server.

(Q4) If the last reply is received (indicated by **replyno_last**) the client is unblocked and ready for further activities.

Query with replication of servers

The more interesting case is where servers are replicated. Here the client must identify which reply message belongs to which server (still allowing for out-of-order receptions). The client initiation and the replies of each server are as before in the case without server replication. However, the client site code for the consumption of the replies has to be modified, as shown in the following.

(Qr3) *client*: consume first reply of first server
client(*C*,**blocked**(1),*query_Id*)
 ⊙ **msg_reply**(*first_server_Id*,1,*query_Id*,*result*)
 ⊙ CONSUME(*first_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*)
 & **client**(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,2),*query_Id*).

(Qr4) *client*: consume first and last reply of first server
client(*C*,**blocked**(1),*query_Id*)
 ⊙ **msg_reply**(*first_server_Id*,**replyno_last**,1,*query_Id*,*result*)
 ⊙ CONSUME(*first_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*)
 & **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*).

(Qr5) *client*: consume *replyno*-th reply of first server
client(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)

@ **msg_reply**(*first_server_Id*,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*first_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,*replyno* + 1),*query_Id*).

(Qr6) *client*: consume *replyno*-th and last reply of first server
client(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)

@ **msg_reply**(*first_server_Id*,**replyno_last**,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*first_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*).

(Qr7) *client*: consume first reply of another server
client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*)

@ **msg_reply**(*other_server_Id*,1,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*other_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*)
 & **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(*other_server_Id*,2),*query_Id*).

(Qr8) *client*: consume first and last reply of another server
client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*)

@ **msg_reply**(*other_server_Id*,**replyno_last**,1,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*other_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*).

(Qr9) *client*: consume *replyno*-th reply of another server

client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(*other_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)
 @ **msg_reply**(*other_server_Id*,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*other_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → **client**(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(*other_server_Id*,*replyno* + 1),*query_Id*).

(Qr10) *client*: consume *replyno*-th and last reply of another server

client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(*other_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)
 @ **msg_reply**(*other_server_Id*,**replyno_last**,*replyno*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 @ CONSUME(*other_server_Id*,*query_Id*,*result*)
 → #t.

The rules (Qr1) and (Qr2) are as before in the non-replicated case.

(Qr3) The blocked client that is triggered by the first reply message with the corresponding *query_Id* consumes this first result offered by the first server that answers. Then the client blocks for the second reply to be received from the same server.

(Qr4) If the first reply is also the last reply to be received (indicated through **replyno_last**) the client is unblocked and ready for further activities. In both cases, an additional client is created that is blocked to receive the replies of another server.

The rules (Qr5) and (Qr6) catch the follow-up replies of the first server.

The rules (Qr7) and (Qr8) catch the first reply of another server. If the other server sends at once the last reply, there is no need to unblock the client. In both cases, simply an additional client is created that is blocked to receive the replies of any further servers.

The rules (Qr9) and (Qr10) catch the follow-up replies of another server. As soon as the last reply arrives, this additionally created client terminates. Note that in all of these rules, that even when the last message **msg_reply**(*server*(*S*),**replyno_last**,*n*,*query_Id*,*result*) arrives too early (i.e., the client has not yet received/consumed all messages from $1 \dots n - 1$) the client will not be unblocked. The client is still in a state **client**(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,*k*),*query_Id*) with $k \in$

$\{1, \dots, n - 1\}$ and the last-reply handling rule cannot be satisfied yet. The same holds of course for `client(C,blocked_other_server(other_server_Id,replyno),query_Id)`. In other words, all replies are consumed in sequence. It is worth mentioning that this scheme exploits the fact that unconsumed messages are held by the runtime environment until they are explicitly consumed, i.e., until the message is a resource on the left-hand side of a rule which fires.

As in the RPC-case, for every single query there exists a client process that consumes the follow-up server-replies of the `query_Id`-request that is already handled. For the same reason as discussed before, we have not shown a termination policy for these processes yet (the timer-controlled policy will manage this). Again we do not know how many reply messages will be received for a single query and, more important, how many servers will answer.

However, during the lifetime of our system only one (additional) process per query will be created, in contrast to one per reply. This is due to the fact that the last reply can be identified, and the process can be terminated as shown in the rule (Qr10).

As far as problem-oriented programming is concerned, we have already mentioned the need for replication. The next step is to implement replication policies within the toolkit in order to increase availability as well as to realize performance gains. In fact, a variety of distributed system approaches use some sort of replication scheme. For a comprehensive survey see [11].

Amongst others, replication can be exploited in two different ways: Firstly, it can be used to mask system failures such as node crashes, or secondly, it can be used to speed up workflow throughput by sending out the same task to different “agent”-replicas. As soon as the “fastest agent” has replied, the next step in the workflow can be triggered. All RPCs or queries are then sent to the pool of replicated agents that may fulfill the required task in parallel and fully independently. Furthermore, the pool of replicated agents can be installed on different hosts to increase availability. If some of the agents have crashed or are not reachable over the network, the client can still receive replies from one of the remaining available agents.

The degree of replication can be dynamically adjusted to special needs or particular pattern of the network (current load, link failure ratio, etc.). What is needed is only a simple decision making routine within the client. We have shown how a client can react to replies from different servers to the same RPC-request or the same query. Take for instance the rule (Qr4), i.e., the first rule within a client to receive the first (and last) reply of the “fastest” server of a query. When, in this rule, the resource `client(C,blocked_other_server(1),query_Id)` is deleted, a client is created that is only interested in the first server to answer, no matter which server that is. All redundant replies of other servers are then ignored, i.e., if we have a write-all-read-any scheme and all but one server crash, the system can still read without harm to the task to fulfill.

2.3 The notion of time

Distributed applications need some notion of time. Some applications may require the execution of a particular function at a concrete timepoint (e.g., given by a resource `time("12:02:34")`), or within a given interval of time (e.g., given by a resource `time_interval("12:00:00-12:05:00")`) or, most importantly, may react to the network delays or site crashes through a timeout. Most policies within distributed communication rely on timeout signals, e.g., given by a resource `timeout(T)` where T is a variable holding the seconds to wait at least until the timeout should occur. In this sense `timeout(5)` should imply a timeout in 5 seconds. We say “should imply a timeout in 5 seconds” because of the following LO-characteristics: since the underlying language LO that is used to implement the toolkit is asynchronous and does not provide real-time features, we must handle timeouts in another way. For us, a timeout is simply an upper bound that, when reached, will eventually trigger a timeout handling routine.

To be more precise, let’s assume the following scenario: a client sends out a RPC-request as

given by the rules in the above examples. Together with the request it sets a timeout value, i.e., a time interval that is the minimum period the client will wait for responses. If the timeout occurs the client will evaluate the responses (or no responses at all) and take a decision whether to proceed normally or to invoke some failure handling routine.

In a replicated server environment, the client may use a policy that guarantees the consistency of the server data through the so-called *majority consensus*.² A request for update is then successful if and only if the majority of servers have fulfilled the update. As long as the majority of servers has not replied to the request, the client must not commit the update. After the timeout, the client checks whether or not the majority has been reached and takes a commit or abort decision. Of course if all servers reply within the given amount of time no timeout handling is done.

The timeout control, i.e., who is responsible for storing the set timeout value T and for signaling the timeout, can be handled within the toolkit in two different ways. Firstly, the client itself can store the timeout value T and check (in a busy-wait loop) whether or not the timeout condition is satisfied. Secondly, the client can spawn a *timer agent* that is provided with the timer value. The client sleeps (or accepts incoming messages) as long as the timer agent does not signal the timeout or, in our given example, all servers have replied.

For the implementation both variants have more or less the same behavior. Since LO-agents never sleep (but, they always check the resource space for possible satisfaction of a rule to fire) the signal of the timer agent is a resource provided to the agent resource space that may then trigger a timeout-handling-rule to fire. This checking in the resource space for the timeout-resource is as expensive as the busy-wait described in the first variant.

As a matter of fact, the provision of the timeout-resource is not a signal as known e.g. from Unix. There, immediately when the runtime priority allows it, the corresponding process is interrupted and in the end set to run the timeout-routing. In LO the time for firing a rule cannot be predicted and depends heavily on the number of active agents, number of rules, and other system parameters that change dynamically.

Therefore, our timeout model is a simulation of the behavior of a “normal” timeout in the sense that we wait at least $T + \Delta t$ sec., where Δt is positive and depending on the parameters just described.

Since, however, we do not intend to provide real-time features, we believe that this timeout model satisfies the needs of almost all network communication protocols that will be build using the toolkit. Often it is even not necessary to have a real clock timer but an incremental counter, as proposed by e.g. Lamport’s algorithm [16] or all voting algorithms we know of [10]. The LoKit-solution concerning the notion of time and timeouts is as follows.

Timer rule

(T) *timer: main rule*

timer(C, Id, T)

@ WAIT(T)

@ ^**timeout**(C, Id)

→ #t.

(T) We install an agent, called *timer*, that plays the role of a clock. The timer waits the given amount of time. Then it simply broadcast the timeout message with the given specification. As usual, there is a binding between timer-invocation and timeout delivery.

²*Majority consensus* is just one of the schemes to maintain consistency among replicated data. Other schemes include *write-all-read-any*, *primary copy*, *quorum consensus*, or the flood of *voting* approaches; see [10] for a survey.

Timer setting

To initiate a timer-controlled communication, the first rule of our communication styles is simply enhanced by the creation, i.e. the setting, of a timer. The following rules *replace* the corresponding rules, e.g., (Qr1_t) replaces rule (Qr1).

(R1_t) and (Rr1_t) *client: initiate RPC-request (timer-controlled)*

```
client(C)
@ GET_UNIQUE(RPC_Id)
@ some_trigger
@ ^msg_request(RPC_Id,param0,...,paramN)
→ client(C,blocked,RPC_Id)
& timer(C,RPC_Id,T).
```

(Q1_t) and (Qr1_t) *client: initiate query-request (timer-controlled)*

```
client(C)
@ GET_UNIQUE(query_Id)
@ some_trigger
@ ^msg_query(query_Id,param0,...,paramN)
→ client(C,blocked(1),query_Id)
& timer(C,query_Id,T).
```

(R1_t) and (Q1_t) The timer is “created” when a client sends out a request. Thereby, the client specifies itself (*C*), the request that should be timer-controlled or better timeout-controlled (*Id*), and, finally, the timeout value itself (*T*), i.e., the time the client is willing to wait for the reply before it wants to be interrupted. Consequently, all client instantiations, i.e.,

- the clients waiting for the RPC-reply (with and without replication of servers),
- the clients waiting for the first reply of a query-request (with and without replication), and
- the clients waiting for follow-up replies to a given query-requests

must have an additional rule that handles the timeout. Depending on the kind of client instantiation, there are different reactions to the timeout as shown in the following rules.

Remark: Since the timer is implemented on the client site, the rules on the server sites (i.e., (R2), (Rr2), etc.) are not affected.

Timer-controlled RPC

To handle timeouts, the following rules must be *added* to the corresponding rule sets, e.g., the rules (Rr3_t) and (Rr3_t) are added to the rule set consisting of the rules (Rr1_t),(Rr2),(Rr3),(Rr4).

(R3_t) and (Rr3_t) *client: consume RPC-reply (timeout)*

```
client(C,blocked,RPC_Id)
@ timeout(C,RPC_Id)
@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT
→ client(C).
```

(Rr4_t) *catch-follow-up client: consume other RPC-reply (timeout)*

```
client(C,catch_follow-up,RPC_Id)
@ timeout(C,RPC_Id)
@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT
→ #t.
```

In the non-replicated as well as replicated case of an RPC, we re-install the client with the rules (R3_t) and (Rr3_t), respectively. In the replicated case we, furthermore, terminate the catch-follow-up client in rule (Rr4_t). As a side-effect, we always terminate the last catch-follow-up client that would otherwise run forever. This is a useful feature of our timeout policy.

Timer-controlled query

The rules for timeout-handling within our query-style communication are analogously formed as illustrated below. They must also be *added* to the corresponding rule sets.

(Q3_t) and (Qr3_t) *client: consume first reply of first server (timeout)*

client(*C*,**blocked**(1),*query_Id*)

@ **timeout**(*C*,*query_Id*)

@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT

→ **client**(*C*).

(Q4_t) and (Qr4_t) *client: consume replyno-th reply of first server (timeout)*

client(*C*,**blocked**(*first_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)

@ **timeout**(*C*,*query_Id*)

@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT

→ **client**(*C*).

(Qr5_t) *client: consume first reply of another server (timeout)*

client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(1),*query_Id*)

@ **timeout**(*C*,*query_Id*)

@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT

→ **#t**.

(Qr6_t) *client: consume replyno-th reply of another server (timeout)*

client(*C*,**blocked_other_server**(*other_server_Id*,*replyno*),*query_Id*)

@ **timeout**(*C*,*query_Id*)

@ APPLICATION-DEPENDENT POLICY FOR TIMEOUT

→ **#t**.

In the non-replicated as well as in the replicated case of a query, we re-install the client with the rules (Q3_t) and (Q4_t) as well as (Qr3_t) and (Qr4_t), respectively. Furthermore, in the replicated case we terminate the unwanted catch-follow-up clients with the rules (Qr5_t) and (Qr6_t).

Fig. 2 illustrates the different roles during the timer-controlled query processing. In the given scenario three identical servers are installed. The query-request has been sent to all of them. We assume that server(1) replies first, then server(3), and finally, server(2). Every time the first reply message of a new server is received, a catch-follow-up client is created. We assume, in addition, that every reply to the query results in two separate reply messages that are sent back to the client host. In the beginning, the client has set a timer. After the specified amount of time the timer sends timeout messages to all client instantiations, i.e., to the original client and all newly created catch-follow-up clients.

3 Remote banking

One of the project's application domains is in the area of remote banking. Remote banking becomes an attractive domain and very effective approach for fulfilling the potentialities that emerge from the following observations:

- electronic and geographically dispersed banking services according to today's merchant requirements have the primary function to provide easy access to, e.g., customer information accounts;
- customers may process their requests from the customer sites to the remote bank sites through public and corporate networks;

Figure 2: Timer-controlled query processing.

- customers may have abstract interfaces for uniform access to the basic banking services offered by different branches and for managing the coordination-critical dialogue among such services;
- corporate customers may have direct access (e.g., for read-only accesses or cash transfers within well-defined boundaries) to their current accounts without directly interacting with the account owners, the banks.

Remote banking as our choice for a distributed application domain is furthermore motivated by the fact that it addresses a broad spectrum of users like end-users, subscribers of particular services, basic service providers (BSP), and value added service providers (VASP). It addresses, moreover, a variety of state-of-the art technology like computing over wide area networks. In its simplest form, the VASP servers enable the creation of customized versions of remote banking services based on some criteria, e.g., input from customers and banks, available banking services such as deposits, withdrawals, or money transfers, corresponding requirements of the customers, technology used by customers and banks such as operating system platforms and finally, telecommunication idiosyncrasies. Schael and Zeller describe in [20] a banking workflow system for particular financial services using a method based on a client-server model, or as they call it, client-supplier model.

The main focus lies on the design of a VASP which provides end-users and subscribers of particular services with simplified access to the basic services offered by the BSPs. Furthermore, the VASP should allow for composite services according to some cost/revenue functions or some broker services. These broker services are capable of dynamically selecting basic services w.r.t. user needs and user-given constraints. Rapid customization should be achieved both on a subscriber basis (e.g., a department of a corporate customer) and on an end-user basis (e.g., employees in a department of a corporate customer).

<i>some_trigger</i>	description of task
LOOKUP	shows all accounts of all banks.
LOOKUP(B)	shows all accounts of bank B .
LOOKUP(B,A)	shows account A of bank B .
DEPOSIT(B,A,Am)	adds amount Am to account A of bank B .
WITHDRAW(B,A,Am)	subtracts amount Am from account A of bank B if and only if there is no overdraft at A .
TRANSFER(B_1,A_1,Am,B_2,A_2)	transfers amount Am from account A_1 of bank B_1 to account A_2 of bank B_2 if and only if there is no overdraft at A_1 .
CREATE(B,A)	creates account A at bank B if and only if this account does not exist already.
DELETE(B,A)	deletes account A at bank B if and only if this account has balance 0.

Remarks: In the current implementation, LOOKUP starts a query whereas all other triggers result in RPCs. In response to a LOOKUP, the corresponding servers return the statement list of every account in a separate message. A statement list includes the balance and the transaction history of the account together with detailed information on attempts to overdraw the account.

TRANSFER(B_1,A_1,Am,B_2,A_2) is part of a higher layer and is built on top of the two constructs DEPOSIT(B_2,A_2,Am) and WITHDRAW(B_1,A_1,Am). The transfer is *atomic* with nested transactional behavior [18].

Table 1: Possible tasks of a remote banking client.

To demonstrate the power of LoKit, we implemented a first prototype of such a remote banking example with distributed replicated databases, i.e., each of a pre-defined number of servers is in charge of a replica of the database. The consistency scheme uses a *write-all-read-any* policy; replication transparency is provided. There may be multiple servers for each bank with separate processes running on (perhaps) different hosts. Within our local area network, the processes are connected through sockets. Over a wide area network, we have already experimented with email as transport mechanism. A client process that gets in contact with a bank (or in contact with more banks where appropriate) can trigger one of the tasks shown in Tab. 1.

During the development of the distributed coordination there is a need to test the failure transparency of the proposed strategies, i.e., masking of network and link failures. Therefore the toolkit provides means for simulating these kind of failures. As a first approach, network failures (especially partitionings) and failstop site crashes [21] can be simulated using the additional triggers SUSPEND(S) or RESUME(S) to suspend or resume the execution of a server S , respectively. The first results are impressive and show that LoKit could be used for rapid prototyping and simulation of distributed applications.

The current implementation of the toolkit runs on Unix-workstations. Ports to other platforms are planned.

4 Future work

The following list summarizes the possible evolution of LoKit as a basic toolkit for the use within distributed applications. First of all, an interface to LoKit should be designed that could be used for rapid prototyping LoKit-based applications. Since the rules provided by LoKit allow for safe and systematic programming, this interface could play the role of a compiler that creates LoKit rules that are then interpreted by the underlying LO-platform. The interface could have the form

of a template where all the application-specific parts of the rules (i.e., underlined resources in the rule set given before) are typed in. Together with explicitly formulated predicate-libraries (for the time being, in Prolog), the template will be a sort of graphical application programming interface.

We already started the implementation of an availability policy using atomic replicated transfers to provide a sophisticated demonstration of the language and the power of the toolkit itself. Fig. 3 illustrates atomic replicated transfers using an atomic broadcasting feature.

Figure 3: Atomic replicated transfers using atomic broadcasting.

Atomic broadcast can be used within a variety of different applications where replicated agents that run on different hosts must fulfill a given task as an atomic action. That also means that the client must have a way to distinguish between successful and unsuccessful executions triggered by broadcasts. We will use version numbers on the raw data that are manipulated during the remote executions. Using these version numbers and some atomicity policy, the client can decide whether to rollback an execution on a remote machine or not (see also [7]).

An important part of LoKit is a constraint-based knowledge broker where agents can proceed even with partial knowledge. An example application is document merging. Here a merging agent collects a number of documents that are needed to create a merged document in some form. However, for timing reasons or other exceptional behavior, not all the necessary documents are provided in time; the merging agents must make a decision on the documents ready so far. Using constraints and making explicit use of partial knowledge, a new intermediate document state may be reached. Later, when more documents are available, more knowledge can be incorporated.

Another area of interest concerns security. Obviously, there are problems arising when every agent in the network has full access to broadcast information as well as to the activities of all other agents. This becomes more severe for large hierarchically structured environments with changing demands for security. In these cases the dynamic behavior should be enhanced by appropriate ask-and-grant mechanisms to restrict the access to agents' private information. An example application is remote banking where user and administration people are distinguished. Both groups of user may have different access rights. For example, admin people may create/delete accounts whereas normal users may only access their own accounts to print statement lists, etc.

Furthermore, a debugging facility is needed that shows – in the best of all worlds – the dynamic behavior of the concurrent activities in a graphical way with symbolic notation. A first step could be to show all agents ready to fire a broadcast message together with the implied resource allocation afterwards.

Finally, LoKit will be enhanced to provide linguistic support for asynchronous communication such as asynchronous RPCs.

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